

Are Maxwell's Electromagnetic Equations Probabilistic?

Francesco R. Ruggeri, Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 26, 2022

We have argued in previous notes (1) that the "wave" nature of quantum mechanics follows from the Lorentz invariant for a constant p : $A = -Et + px$ which holds for both a particle with rest mass and a photon. In A , t and x are separated indicating independence which violates the Newtonian view $x(t)$. " A " leads to $\partial A / \partial x = p$ and $\partial A / \partial t = -E$. Creating eigenvalue equations yields: $-i \partial / \partial x \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ and $i \partial / \partial t \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt)$. Thus, x and t may be separated. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ exists in all of space (because there is no time), it represents a somewhat spatially invariant probability.

In the case of a photon, Maxwell showed one may write wave equations for the electric E and magnetic B fields using his electromagnetic equations with no charge or currents. He showed the wave travels at the speed of light in a vacuum and thus characterized light as an electromagnetic wave. This is not the same statement as $\exp(ipx)$ which is a probability wave. One may note that Maxwell's equations are Lorentz invariant, so the ideas of the first paragraph should hold. In this note, however, we consider the Poynting equation: $\partial / \partial t (\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + 1/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + 1/\mu_0 \text{grad} \cdot E \times B = \text{function}(\text{charge and current})$. $1/\mu_0 E \times B$ is considered to be a momentum density. We note Maxwell's equations contain $\partial / \partial t$ and $\partial / \partial x$, so time and space are considered independent (unlike $x(t)$), and act on E and B . The presence of charge and current densities breaks spatial invariance i.e. creates local regions.

We argue in this note that $\partial / \partial x$ and $\partial / \partial t$ are generators of translations in space and time. We further argue that Maxwell's theoretical creation of a photon follows from introducing spatial invariance into the problem, i.e. removing all charge and current densities. Spatial invariance in Newtonian mechanics, however, is associated with a constant i.e. a constant speed and momentum and equal probability to be at any x . Given that $\partial / \partial x$ and $\partial / \partial t$ appear, one has a function of space and time which seems to be completely at odds with spatial invariance and the idea of a constant momentum. We have argued in (2), however, that constant motion, even though represented by $v = \text{constant}$, is associated with the force that created the momentum, and this manifests itself in a spatial density which is probabilistic. Thus the presence of $\partial / \partial t$ and $\partial / \partial x$ in Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, even when charge and current densities are removed, implies the same thing. Thus we argue that Maxwell's electromagnetic equations are probabilistic. We investigate these ideas in this note. We further argue that it is spatial invariance, together with the presence of $\partial / \partial x$ which yields the periodic form $\exp(ipx)$. Thus it is not a coincidence that wave equations appear for E and B .

Special Relativity

We have argued previously that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ is the source of the quantum wavelength and frequency i.e. \hbar/p and \hbar/E . This internal length gradation and clock gradation maintain A constant. $\partial A / \partial x = p$ and $-\partial A / \partial t = E$. " x " and " t " are separated and independent, so this scheme differs from Newton's $x(t)$, although on average $x(t) = \text{constant}$ is satisfied. The eigenfunctions in this problem are:

$$-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((1b))$$

X and t are separated in A, so we consider $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ independently, if possible, in problems. Momentum is created through an impulse, so we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ should carry information about the force which created it. This, we suggest, is the reason for the two probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ (see (2)). There does not exist deterministic motion, i.e. acceleration associated with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ for the following reason:

Deterministic acceleration would contradict the deterministic $v=\text{constant}$ which suggests a constant probability at all x points. Acceleration (even speeding up and then down so that an average speed of $v=\text{constant}$ is achieved within a wavelength) suggests a different spatial density i.e. one that is not spatially invariant. Deterministic acceleration also suggests an external force as given by Newton's second law. We argue that the information about the force with created the momentum must be encoded statistically, although with a fixed distribution.

The probabilistic approach assumes a probability density. This means that within a wavelength one does not know where the particle is (even though it has fixed p). At the same time, the particle is moving in a certain direction, so one needs two distributions to account for such a situation. Treating these as two dimensions allows one to create a periodic function which has a modulus of 1 pointing to:

$$\cos(px) + i \sin(px) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

We note that the above arguments apply equally to a particle with rest mass and a photon.

Maxwell's Electromagnetic Equations

Maxwell's electromagnetic equations are Lorentz invariant and were used by Maxwell to solve for a photon. Thus one might expect that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ discussed above should apply to the photon as should $\exp(ipx)$. In this note, however, we wish to consider the photon without using special relativity or even Maxwell's wave solutions, but to focus on spatial invariance.

We begin by noting that Maxwell's EM equations use partial derivatives $\frac{d}{dt}$ partial and $\frac{d}{dx}$ partial suggesting time and space are independent. This is interesting because if a photon solution is found, it has a constant speed such that $x(t)=ct$ in a vacuum, so there is a contradiction, unless one thinks of the x,t independence in the same as in $A = -Et + px$. Secondly, we note that Maxwell's EM equations usually contain charge and current densities. In order to "create" a photon solution, one must set all charge and current densities to zero and create a spatially invariant system.

As argued in the above section, a spatially invariant system is associated with a constant speed and momentum in Newtonian mechanics and treats all x points the same. If this is the case, however, can one have $\frac{d}{dx}$ in the problem? Consider the Poynting equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} .5(\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + 1/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + 1/\mu_0 \text{grad} \cdot (E \times B) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

for the photon case. If one assumes that there are only constants in the problem to remove x, t dependence, one has energy density and momentum density in all of space which is constant. One might try to associate this with a constant value at each x ignoring time, and then consider a constant again at each time, ignoring x . This is what one does in quantum mechanics for a particle i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ and $\exp(-iEt)\exp(iEt)=1$, but $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ are not constant. ((3)) is reminiscent of the photon dispersion relation $E=pc$ if $c=x/t$. This suggests one may have a kind of spatial invariance and still have dynamics. Thus d/dx and d/dt do not act on constants. This suggests the same arguments made in section 1, namely that one may consider x and t separately and each corresponds to a spatial or time distribution linked with the generators d/dx and d/dt which also appear in ((3)). The eigenfunctions which yield a somewhat invariant solution are $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$.

Thus, we argue that spatial invariance linked directly with the generator d/dx (and separately time invariance linked with the generator d/dt) govern the solution of the photon. In other words, setting charge and current densities to zero in Maxwell's EM equations and still insisting on physical EM momentum (as in ((3))), means the solution is governed by the generators d/dx and d/dt . As a result, it is not a coincidence that Maxwell's equations happen to yield wave solutions for E and B . There seems to be no other choice, if one ignores a constant solution.

Arguing that the spatial distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are linked to probabilities, because they cannot be linked to deterministic acceleration, we argue that Maxwell's equations as well as $A = -Et + px$ are associated with probabilistic behaviour linked to momentum impulses which create momentum in the first place and "remain" in the moving object manifested as spatial distributions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, which contain d/dt partial and d/dx partial treat x and t as independent. They also break spatial invariance in the presence of local charge and current densities which are not spatially invariant. If one tries, as Maxwell did, to remove local features, i.e. charge and current densities, one is left with equations with d/dt partial and d/dx partial which represent spatial invariance. The Poynting equation which follows from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations shows one may have electromagnetic energy and momentum densities. Setting charge and current densities to zero implies spatial invariance i.e. a kind of constant EM momentum density. " X " and " t ", however, are independent which violates Newton's $d/dt x(t) = \text{constant}$ result. If one does not wish to have a trivial constant solution, the next solution which maps to a constant solution is to consider eigenfunctions of d/dx and d/dt (or rather $-id/dx$, id/dt) which yield somewhat invariant (i.e periodic) solutions $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$.

As a result, we argue it is not a coincidence that Maxwell's EM equations yield wave equations for the electric and magnetic fields in the absence of charge and current densities. This result, we argue, may be anticipated through the invariance arguments we have given. We also note that special relativity $A = -Et + px$ yields the same result and that Maxwell's EM equations are Lorentz invariant. Thus this separate argument also seems to lead to the idea of $\exp(-iEt)$ $\exp(ipx)$.

The form $\exp(ipx)$ contains two spatial probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ due to stored force information, so we argue Maxwell's EM equations are probabilistic i.e. not strictly deterministic.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flux/Flow Scheme (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Free Particle//Photon Energy, Information, Force and Spacetime (preprint, zenodo, 2023)